

Impact of Bollywood and changing Marriage practices

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Abstract

Marriage provides emotional component companionship. Social support, procreation and family formation and legal and financial benefit that contribute to the stability and security of individuals and families. Furthermore, marriage acts as a social institution that helps to create sense of belonging and social support. Every Single custom & practice in wedding ceremony has deep philosophical and spiritual significance. Bollywood or Hindi film industry is one of the biggest film industries. Hindi cinema has always been a major point of reference for Indian culture and society. Bollywood the big player in Indian movies has become a major influence. It does not only shape weddings in India but its impact is also felt globally. This paper aims to analysis the changing Indian marriage practices due to Bollywood

Keywords: Bollywood, Marriage Practice, Institution

Introduction

The evolution of concept of marriage is difficult thing to trace because birth of man is birth of marriage. Marriage is practice that seems as human race itself. Man is social animal hence enjoys the company of his fellow human beings. To enjoy the various fruits of life, it was essential to regulate the behavior of group member for which he has developed various institutions, Marriage is one of old vital institution.

Radha Krishan (1956) writes, “Marriage is not a mere convention but an implicit condition of human society, it is an adjustment between the biological purpose of nature and Sociological purpose of man”

Dictionary of Sociology, Duccan Mitchell (1978), “Socially sanctioned sex relation involving two or more people of the opposite sex whose relation is expected to endure beyond time required for gestation and the birth of children.

Marriage provides emotional component companionship. Social support, procreation and family formation and legal and financial benefit that contribute to the stability and security of individuals and families. It greats sense of belonging and communities providing a stable environment for raising children. Furthermore, marriage acts as a social institution that helps to create sense of belonging and social support. It provides

individuals with a network of family and friends, creating a community of support & connection. Indian marriages, accordingly to belief are made in heaven and once you are married is supposed to last for seven lifetimes. Indian weddings are a long process with various rituals that may take days to be executed. Every Single custom & practice in wedding ceremony has deep philosophical and spiritual significance. Trough out the world, Indians adhere to these set of rituals and continue on the traditions rituals and continue on the traditions of the marriage that are unique amongst those in the world.

Globalization, Media and Bollywood

Cinema is a potent medium for reflecting the culture and ethos of any society. Bollywood or Hindi film industry is one of the biggest film industries. Hindi cinema has always been a major point of reference for Indian culture and society. Not only has it shaped but also expressed the changing scenarios and contours of India's cultural and societal sentiments to such an extent that no other preceding art form could ever achieve. In 1990-1991 the Indian economy experienced a serious economic downturn, due to which new financial policies were implemented. As a result of the new policies, India could open up its economic gates to investments from the West. This change in India's approach towards a more open economy came to be known as liberalization. Liberalization brought along with it not only foreign investments but also cultural influences. Liberalization also brought technological influxes, allowing new satellite channels to take over Indian broadcasting. New satellite channels meant new content; this new content was not nationalistic in nature but was heavily influenced by Western programming standards. This change was also reflected within popular cultures, like cinema and television. These media forms are essential sites that deal with changes in culture and traditions. Wedding serves as a lens through which the amalgamation of wedding tradition can be observed. Indian wedding used to be simple traditional. But in recent years, something new has happened. Bollywood the big player in Indian movies has become a major influence. It does not only shape weddings in India but its impact is also felt globally. With the glitz and glamour of Bollywood mixing with old traditions weddings are changing.

- **The Shoe stealing Game (Joota Chupai)**

Hiding the shoes or the Jutti Chupai ritual is done when the couple reaches the mandap for 'Pheras'. The groom, the groom gets m removes his shoes and sits for the main wedding act. Through the wedding ceremonies the girls from the brides side search for an opportunity to steal groom's shoes and hide them in secret place. Meanwhile, the boys from groom's side try their best not to allow the girls succeed in stealing the groom's shoes. After the ceremony complete the groom gets up to leave hall and search for his shoes. However, bridesmaids surround him to demand some money in exchange foe his shoes. The groom has no choice inspite of lot of begging and pleading he has to pay the amount and then allowed to put on his shoes.

This was not a custom in Indian marriages until late 1990's. This idea was copied from famous bollywood movie, 'Hum Aapke Hai Kaun' (1994) This was the major impact of bollywood in real life wedding.

- **Sangeet, Mehendi and Haldi**

The word Sangeet translated to 'sung together' from Sanskrit. Traditionally celebrated in the Punjab regions of India. This ceremony has been adopted by many other regions as a form of celebration for the wedding. The event is formally known to comprise of only female attendees from both sides of the family, however modern times allows for men to join in on the fun too. There are many movies where we can see this ceremony has portrayed. e.g. Dilwale Dulhaniya Le Jayenge, Hum Sath Sath Hai, Veere di Wedding etc. all these movies belong to north Indian culture. But we can see this ceremony has spread throughout India. Even in South India, rest over nation and remote villages is also practicing this ceremony. Many songs and dance steps are adopted from famous movies. Movies are succeeded in spreading this culture even in remote villages. Same goes with mehendi and Haldi ceremony. People are practicing and adopting this ceremony in their wedding.

- **Cake Cutting**

Cake cutting was never been part of Indian tradition. Like many other things in modern India, cutting cakes on birthday is influenced by western culture. Now a day cake is being cut in wedding ritual as well. We can see this happening even in remote villages. This is one of the major changes in Indian marriages. Cake cutting is depicted as an act of rich people to celebrate an occasion in various Indian movies, almost since half-a-century. This is ingrained into people. To cut a cake will help to show off the “richness” that one has. It was very common to cut cake on birthdays and anniversaries, but now a days there is culture being developed to cut cake on wedding and ring ceremony too.

- **Pre Wedding and Post Wedding Photoshoot**

Social media has played a significant role in the rise of pre and post wedding shoots. Another factor that has contributed to the rise of pre and post wedding shoots is the advancement of technology. The impact of Covid 19 has also played a very crucial role to develop these trends as to cancel and postpone the wedding and other celebration. Everyone has found alternatives for wedding documentation and to celebrate their love. Pre-post wedding shoots offer a safe and unique way for couples to capture their love and commitment to each other. While shoot couple follows all celebrity look, pose and the famous bollywood songs. Social media platform has made it easier for couples to find inspiration for their photoshoot.

- **Other**

With all these things there are other things also impact the changing marriage practice in a modern India like, choreographed dance, Destination wedding, Bride-Groom entry, Costumes, Jewelry, Changing food culture, Themed Decoration etc.

Conclusion

People incorporate Bollywood trends into weddings. This happens when elements are chosen without proper understanding of their cultural meaning. There is a risk of cultural appropriation. The problem here is that traditions can be turned into just rich fashionable trends, which might spread stereotypes and make the original culture seen less genuine. It’s like taking something important from a culture and using it as a fashion statement without truly respecting or understanding its significance and importance. This can be harmful because it doesn’t honor the depth and authenticity of the culture involved.

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